
STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC STUDY OF THE ANTHROPONYMS STATED IN HOLY KORAN AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Zilola Melikuzieva Qahramon kizi

zilolamelikuzieva@gmail.com

Ferghana State University

Direction: Linguistics (English)

2-course master

+998997273312

Qahramon Sulaymonov

Ferghana State University

Director of Master's Department

Abstract.

The article discusses the concept of anthroponyms given in holy book Koran and its role in modern linguistics.

Keywords.

anthroponymy, vocabulary, anthroponyms, surnames, onomastics, toponyms, prophet .

Introduction

Anthroponymy (also anthroponymics or anthroponomastics, from Ancient Greek *anthrōpos* / 'human', and *onoma* / 'name') is the study of anthroponyms, the proper names of human beings, both individual and collective. Anthroponymy is a branch of onomastics.

Researchers in the field of anthroponymy are called anthroponymists. Since the study of anthroponyms is relevant for several other disciplines within social sciences and humanities, experts from those disciplines engage in anthroponymic studies, including researchers from the fields of anthropology, history, human geography, sociology, prosopography, and genealogy.

Anthroponymists are required to follow certain principles, rules and criteria when researching anthroponyms. The methods used for research are divided into two major categories: the collecting of anthroponymic information and the analysis and interpretation of anthroponyms. The collection of anthroponymic information includes: inscriptions, documents, onomastics-tax records, dictionaries, phone

books, monographs, and websites, which are used afterward for mapping purposes. The analysis and interpretation of anthroponyms take into account the processing of the collection of the information gathered, which consists of linguistic analysis, comparative-historical method, geographical method, and statistical method.¹⁵⁷

Main body

Anthroponyms (personal name, nickname and pseudonym (pen name, professional name)¹⁵⁸) are one of the ancient cultural, spiritual and linguistic values of the Uzbek people.¹⁵⁹ Thus, names of historical people and prophets given in holy Koran are considered exact examples of anthroponyms. It can be divided into several types:

- names of prophets
- names of bad people
- names of good people and also male and female names.

There are stated twenty five prophets whose real life stories mentioned in holy Koran. They are : Adam, Idris, Nuh, Hud, Solih, Ibrohim, Lut, Ismail, Ishaq, Ya'qub, Yusuf, Ayyub, Zul kifl, Shuayb, Musa, Harun, Ilyas, Alyasa, Yunus, Davud, Sulayman, Zakariyya, Yahya, Isa, and Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) alayhissalam¹⁶⁰.

“First prophet sent to human beings is Adam alayhissalam, last one is clear Muhammad alayhissalam”¹⁶¹.

We are all descended from Adam, and his origin is the earth (Seitbekov, 2011) This life is fleeting. Adam was created first, And the earth accepted him too, Mashkhur Zhusup (2008) mentions that Adam was the first to be created. From these passages it is clear that he was the first ancestor and first prophet of mankind and has a graceful character.¹⁶²

“Adam, you, live with your spouse in Paradise. What you want to eat, you may taste it, good appetite but do not come closer to this tree, otherwise (if you arrive at next to that tree) you, both of you become tyrant to themselves”¹⁶³

¹⁵⁷ Information from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

¹⁵⁸ Wisdom dictionary. support@wisdomedu.uz. 2020 “Umbrella Soft” tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan ilova.

¹⁵⁹ ANAMASTICS AND ANALYSIS OF THEIR FUNCTIONS IBRATOV BAKHROMBEK BAYZAKOVICH
Lecturer of the Department of Western Languages, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Sep 2020.

¹⁶⁰ History of prophets. Sherzod Atamurodov, Dilfuza Shoyzoqova, T.2016 p 4

¹⁶¹ History of prophets. Sherzod Atamurodov, Dilfuza Shoyzoqova, T.2016 p 10

¹⁶² Abisheva, G., Trushev, A., Zhussupov, N., & Karipzhanova, A. (2022). Religious anthroponyms in the works of Mashkhur Zhusup

¹⁶³ Tafsir al hilol. Shayx Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. 2008. p 36

“And Remember Idris, he was trustworthy(honest) and prophet” so we enhanced his reputation. in surah Maryam, ayah 56 – 57.

“Remember Ibrohim, he was trustworthy(honest) and prophet” narrated in surah Maryam, ayah 41.

Jacob - a common hero of Judaism, Christianity and Islam. Jacob's second name was Israel. From his twelve sons came twelve tribes, who were called the descendants of Israel (Aubakir, 2014). In Mashkhur's works, the onym of Jacob (Ighop) is given as the name of the prophet. Two comrades who were friends before the country: soul and body. The soul is the mother of St. Jacob (Ighop) and the body is the mother of St. Joseph (Mashkhur, 2008a). The name Jacob is also mentioned in the story "Earth and Heaven" by Mashkhur Zhusup: He excelled in mastery knowing seventy-two languages, After that this knowledge became his profession.

First Ishmael was born, Isaac, then Jacob, One was better than the other (Mashkhur, 2005b). After Jacob became blind after losing his son Joseph, obeyed God and chose patience and humility as the meaning of life.¹⁶⁴ “Remember Musa stated in the book. He was a prophet chosen among you and ambassador” given in surah Maryam, ayah 51.¹⁶⁵ and others.

It is found opposite names in the holy book : Tolut and Jalut, Qorun and Hatami Tay.

“Qorun, Fir'avn(emperor who lived in the same period with Muso peace and blessings of Allah be upon him,) and Haman (were killed tragically). Even though Musa proved the existence of God and taught them how to pray, they kept on dissembling when they were alive, however, they could not escape a severe penalty.

“Hatami Tay is extremely generous person who plays important role in history of famous kind people, unfortunately he could not live till our prophet Muhammad alayhissalom.”¹⁶⁶

Today we can easily find such names among not only Uzbek people but also all around the world where muslims live. Example: Muhammadjon, Toshmuhammad, Shermuhammad, Dilmuhammad, Muhammad Bobur, Muhammad Ziyoy, Nurmuhhammad, and so on.

The disgusting image of Abu Jahl in the epic also came from the truth. You can read about this in the Quran, hadith, the sacred "Sira" and studies of Arab

¹⁶⁴ Abisheva, G., Trushev, A., Zhussupov, N., & Karipzhanova, A. (2022). Religious anthroponyms in the works of Mashkhur Zhusup

¹⁶⁵ Tafsir al hilol. Shayx Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. 2008. p547

¹⁶⁶ Курони Карим маъноларнинг таржима ва тафсири. Шайх Абдулазиз Мансур. Тошкент 2021. 58 б

historians (Gzibaeva, 2005). One of the religious poetry names found in Mashkhur's works is Gabriel. Gabriel is the angel closest to Allah who, by the order of Allah, will put his soul into the soulless and support the suffering people. He is the main mediator between Allah and the prophets, including Muhammad (pbuh) Balgasem and Zakaria, 2018; Prochwicz-Studnicka, 2020). Religious legends also describe Gabriel's place in the life of Muhammad (pbuh). He handed the Quran to Muhammad (pbuh) piece by piece during the month of Ramadan. He protected and instructed the prophet, accompanying him on his night journey to Quddus and assisting him in military affairs and religious disputes. Gabriel is the highest of the four angels closest to Allah. Sometimes he is described as standing with his feet on the ground and his head in the clouds (Islam. Encyclopedic..., 2010; Alrumhi, 2021).¹⁶⁷

Religious legends and stories say that the Prophet Solomon (pbuh) possessed great power, great glory and knowledge, and also knew the language of animals and living beings. He is also mentioned in the tale of Mashkhur Zhusup "Solomon and the Ant". Khazret Suleiman repented, paying tribute to the ant, having received many clever thoughts from the ant and agreed with his own ignorance and knowledge of the ant. Let those who will be kings after me learn a lesson from this! Even if someone is as small as an ant, let him listen to what he finds and says (Mashkhur, 2005c).¹⁶⁸

Abu Jahl is the man who shot and betrayed Muhammad in the epic. Abu Jahl fired angrily, Unbelievers offend Muhammad, First he met Abu Jahl, A brave man who offended many people (Mashkhur, 2007).

Anthroponymy of individual and family names, and their mutual correlations, includes the study of:

Personal names, Given names, Surnames, Nicknames, Pseudonyms, Mononyms, Matronyms, Patronyms, Eponyms, Teknonyms.

Anthroponyms of individuals can also be classified according to gender. Names of human males are called andronyms (from Ancient Greek / man, and / name), while names of human females are called gynonyms (from Ancient Greek woman, and / name). Anthroponymy of group and population names includes the study of demonyms (names of localized populations), ethnonyms (names of ethnic groups), as well as tribal names and clan(names of a group of family or tribes) names.

¹⁶⁷ Abisheva, G., Trushev, A., Zhussupov, N., & Karipzhanova, A. (2022). Religious anthroponyms in the works of Mashkhur Zhusup. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 18(1), 372-385. Doi: 10.52462/jlls.188
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¹⁶⁸ That source

Anthroponymy is a socio-cultural tool that can be used to find out about an individual's culture. Through the name of a person, their nationality, as well as their history, can be traced. Anthroponyms have both a national and cultural significance as they guarantee the preservation of linguistics, cultural, and historical information.

There are several specific terms and processes related to anthroponymy, like: anthroponymization, a process when an anthroponym is formed from an appellative, like when a surname is created from the name of occupation, thus forming an occupational surname. Such surnames are common in most languages, including,

English: Smith (from smith), Miller (from miller), Thatcher (from thatcher), Shepherd (from shepherd), or Potter (from potter). deanthroponymization, a process when an anthroponym becomes an appellative, like when the surname of the inventor Louis Braille was used to create a name for the writing system for the visually impaired persons (braille). transonymization of anthroponyms into toponyms, a process when a human proper name is used to form a toponym (proper name of a locality; place name), thus creating an anthropotonym, like when the name of Alexander the Great was used to create several astionyms (city names), including name for the newly created city of Alexandria in the ancient Hellenistic Egypt, or when the surname of Christopher Columbus was used to create several choronyms (region names), including names for Southamerican state of Colombia, and Canadian province of British Columbia. transonymization of toponyms into anthroponyms, a process when toponyms (place names) are used to form human names (anthroponyms), thus creating various topoanthroponyms. Many surnames are created in that way, and they are known as toponymic surnames. Most demonyms (names for localized populations) are topoanthroponyms by formation, since they are usually created from toponyms, and also some ethnonyms are topoanthroponyms too (those that are formed from toponyms, and thus referred to as topoethnonyms). For example, geographic designations for the region of Black Mountain (Montenegro) and frontier region of Ukraina (Ukraine) were used to create not only demonyms for general populations for those regions, but also ethnonyms for modern ethnic Montenegrins and ethnic Ukrainians.¹⁶⁹

Conclusion

¹⁶⁹ from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

In conclusion, in this article, we identified a number of religious anthroponyms from the holy Koran and works of other scientists. Despite their peculiarities, all religious anthroponyms stated in the article are a means of expressing their views in the field of culture and religion.

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- 6) <http://www.rogerdarlington.me.uk/useofnames.html>
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